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Smart-based Monitoring of Epoxy Using Piezoelectric Transducers

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Abstract

Structural adhesives are an important component of strengthening and repair techniques for structures. Adequate and proper curing of such materials is essential to achieve its desired strength and durability. In this study, the curing process of epoxy type Sikadur 330 is monitored using the electromechanical impedance (EMI) technique employing smart piezoelectric material, namely Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT). Experimental results show that the PZT transducer embedded into the epoxy in liquid state is effective in monitoring the initial setting and the subsequent hardening process of a lab scale epoxy coupon. Rightward movement of both the PZT resonance peaks and the structural resonance peaks indirectly reflects the curing process. This study shows that the EMI technique is capable of monitoring the curing process of the structural adhesive. Future study shall focus on developing theoretical model capable of parametrically relate the electrical signatures to the mechanical stiffness and strength.

1. Introduction

Civil engineering discipline has recently witnessed a rise in the use of structural adhesives, in particular Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) reinforcements in strengthening structural systems. Two-part structural epoxy adhesives are the most commonly used adhesive to bond FRP to other structural elements due to their advanced mechanical and chemical properties (Lettieri and Frigione 2012). The FRP materials can be bonded to various structural components including concrete, steel, and timber for repair and strength enhancement reasons.

In FRP strengthened joints materials, the mechanical performance of the joint is directly related to the strength and the stiffness of the epoxy adhesive, particularly during the early stages of installation while the epoxy is still curing and its mechanical properties are evolving. The performance of the FRP joint is strongly dependent on adequate preparation, application and curing of the epoxy resin.

Adhesives undergo various chemical transformations during the curing process. The freshly mixed liquid adhesive converts into a rubber (gelation) and then into a solid glass (vitrification). As the adhesive cures there is increased cross-linking between monomers, developing a progressively more complex polymeric network. For a structural adhesive to reach its targeted bond strength, the necessary curing time is highly dependent on the environmental conditions, particularly temperature and moisture (Czaderski et al 2012). In general, lower curing temperature results in slower curing process, resulting in decelerated rate of development of the epoxy resins mechanical properties. For practical and economic considerations, cold-curing adhesives are more commonly used in the civil engineering discipline.

Monitoring the curing process of adhesive is therefore significant to ensure structural integrity. In this paper, a novel study is conducted to investigate the feasibility of using the smart piezoelectric based electromechanical impedance technique (EMI) in monitoring the curing process of structural adhesive. The advent of smart based health monitoring technique, such as the EMI technique, which employs piezoelectric transducer (PZT) as active sensor shows distinct superiority over its conventional counterpart. It has the potential to provide autonomous, real-time and remote monitoring at relatively low cost with large scale application. The PZT patches can be conveniently attached to various structures as they are generally non-intrusive. With appropriate protection such as using silicone rubber, the PZT transducer is fairly durable and remains operational for years (Yang, Lim & Soh 2008). The PZT patches used in the EMI technique can be installed at various critical structural members for monitoring the structural health. This technique utilizes the transduction capability of PZT to convert electrical energy to mechanical energy and vice versa. With the PZT transducer attached on a host structure, an alternating voltage of varying frequency is applied by an impedance analyser across the poling direction of the transducer. The transducer can thus be excited (converse effect of piezoelectricity) and correspondingly actuates the host structure. On the other hand, the structural vibratory response interacts with the PZT transducer, thus modulating the current passing through the transducer (direct effect of piezoelectricity). The modulated current, in terms of complex electrical admittance, can simultaneously be measured by the impedance analyser. In other words, the admittance signatures contain information pertinent to the modes of vibration of the host structure. Any changes in the vibratory behaviour of the host structure caused by curing of concrete (Tawie and Lee 2011; Lim et al. 2016), presence of damage (Lim and Soh 2011; Soh and Bhalla 2000), change in stress (Lim and Soh 2013) or other changes in mechanical properties can therefore be reflected in the admittance signatures.

2. Experimental Setup

The curing process of a commercially available two parts epoxy, namely Sikadur 330 (Sika, 2014) was monitored in this experiment. Epoxy was first mixed according to the specification and placed into standard mould. Three identical coupon specimens were prepared. The specimens were denoted as S330_1, S330_2 and S330_3, respectively. One PZT patch, dimensioned 10mm x 10mm x 0.3mm, was immediately embedded into the epoxy while it is still in its liquid state. A typical epoxy coupon is shown in Figure 1(a). All specimens were cured inside the laboratory with stable temperature (24⁰C).

Acquisition of signatures was immediately initiated after the PZT patches were embedded to start monitoring the curing process. An impedance analyser (Hioki IM3570) as shown in Figure 1(b) was used to apply a 5V alternating voltage across the PZT transducer and simultaneously record its electrical admittance. A wide range of frequency (5 kHz – 900 kHz) was considered to capture the changes in vibratory behaviour of both the host structure and the PZT patch. Signatures acquisition was performed periodically, one PZT patch at a time. In the first 24 hours, signatures were acquired every hour as the epoxy was undergoing rigorous curing. The interval was reduced to once per day for the next 7 days as the progress of curing retarded considerably. After 7 days, signatures were recorded every other day up to 21 days. The changes in signatures has practically halted after 21 days as the epoxy was fully cured and no further changes in electrical signatures were observed.

Figure 1. Pictorial representation of experimental setup for curing monitoring of epoxy using EMI technique.

3. Repeatability of signatures – freely suspended PZT patches

Typical plot of conductance signatures (real component of electrical admittance) versus frequency spectrum of four freely suspended PZT patches under sinusoidal actuation is schematically presented in Figure 2. Note that the four dominant peaks represent the resonances of the PZT patch. Overlapping of the resonance peaks throughout the entire frequency range suggests that the repeatability of the signatures obtained from different PZT patches is very high.

Figure 2. Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from 4 freely suspended PZT patches (0 – 900 kHz).

4. Monitoring of Curing Process of Epoxy

4.1 PZT Peaks as Indicator

4.1.1 Monitoring of admittance signatures: 1 - 6 hours

The first PZT resonance peak (between 100 and 200 kHz) of Specimen S330_2 is herein examined. In the first 6 hours, the magnitude of the peak reduces rapidly, as shown in Figure 3. The resonance frequency is also gradually reducing, as shown from the leftward movements of the peak with time.

Figure 3: Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from specimen S330_2 in the first 6 hours (300 – 700 kHz).

This phenomenon can be easily related to the physical process. When the PZT patch is first immersed into the epoxy, the epoxy is in its liquid state. The magnitude of the resonance peak of the PZT patch is significantly dampened by the viscosity of the liquid. The resonance frequency of the peak is also reduced indicating that the vibration of the PZT patch is being gradually restrained, indicating that it can no longer vibrate independently (Yang, Lim & Soh 2008).

This process continues to occur within the first 4 hours, to an extent that the peak almost disappears after 3 hours. The PZT's peak, however, reappears after 5 hours.

It is also worth mentioning that, unlike in the first 5 hours, the magnitudes of all the PZT peaks thereafter remain largely constant, indicating that the damping effect caused by the epoxy has reached a stable state.

4.1.2 Monitoring of admittance signatures: 6 – 24 hours

Figure 4(a) depicts the changes of the first PZT resonance peak from 6 hours to 24 hours and thereafter on Specimen S330_2. From 6 to 8 hours, there is a rapid rightward movement of the resonance peak, indicating that the host structure is gaining significant stiffness. Gain in stiffness can be indirectly related to increase in strength. The rightward movement of the resonance peak continues to occur after 8 hours, but at a much lower rate, as summarised in Figure 5a. From the shape of the curve, one could find that all three specimens exhibit very similar trend of increase.

Figure 4: Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from specimen S330_2 after the first 6 hours
 (a) 100 – 300 kHz (b) 160 – 180 kHz

4.1.3 Monitoring of admittance signatures: 1 – 21 days

After one day of curing, the rate of rightward movement of the peak further decreases, as shown in Figure 4(a), where all the peaks after 1 day are nearly overlapping each other. Movement of the peaks can still be clearly identified by zooming into a narrower frequency range (160 – 180 kHz), as shown in Figure 4(b). The change in resonance frequency of the first PZT peak for all three specimens are summarised in Figure 5(b). Moderate increase in frequency occurs from day 1 to 4, and tapers thereafter. Note that peak movement from day 14 to 21 can be considered negligible, indicating that the curing process practically ends at approximately 14 days.

Once again, the trend of increase is consistent among all three specimens but the absolute values are different. This is likely to be caused by the slight variations in geometrical shape of the specimens and boundary conditions of the surrounding mould, as the admittance signatures are extremely sensitive to these local variations (Lim and Soh, 2012).

Figure 5: Resonance frequency of first PZT peak versus time of specimen S330_1, S330_2 and S330_3 after the first 6 hours

(a) first 5 – 24 hours (b) 1 – 21 days

4.2 Host Structural Peaks as Indicator

Previous study (Lim et al. 2011) shows that the densely spaced resonance peaks occurring in the lower frequency range (<100 kHz) are better representation of the vibratory behaviour of the host structure. These peaks are often used to observe the variation of host structural resonances (vibratory behaviour) for the purpose of health monitoring.

In this study, no obvious structural peak can be observed in the first 4 hours, as shown in Figure 6. This indirectly reflects that the epoxy is still in a “liquid” form as significant vibration of the host structure is non-existence. Note that the change in slope of the curves are mainly caused by the movement of the first PZT peaks, which does not affect the host structural behaviour.

However, after 5 hours, trace of resonance peaks can be found, as shown from the curves of “5hr” and “6hr”, indicating that the epoxy is hardening and transforming into solid. This observation agrees well with its counterpart – PZT’s peak (Section 4.1). In addition, referring to the manufacturer’s product data sheet (Sikadur 330, 2014), the “tack free time” of Sikadur 330 is approximately 4 – 5 hours, after which, the epoxy will gain significant stiffness. This outcome proves that the EMI technique is very sensitive to the hardening process and can be a useful indicator of the initial hardening.

Figure 6: Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from specimen S330_2 in the first 6 hours (0 – 100 kHz).

From 8 hours onwards, stronger and clearer structural peaks are formed which can be visually identified, as shown in Figure 7(a). Similar to the behaviour of the PZT peak as presented in previous section, the structural resonance peaks move progressively to the right (increase in resonance frequency) as curing progresses. The rate of movement, once again, indirectly reflects the rate of curing, as shown in Figure 7(b).

Thus, both structural resonance peaks and PZT resonance peaks are useful indicator of the curing process of epoxy. The PZT peaks are especially useful in characterising the early curing (first 1-6 hours), including the initial setting of the epoxy.

Figure 7: Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from specimen S330_2 showing the structural peaks
 (a) 30 – 80 kHz (b) 55 – 59 kHz

5. Conclusion

In this study, the curing process of epoxy Sikadur 330 is monitored using the EMI technique. Experimental results show the PZT transducer is effective in monitoring the initial setting and the subsequent curing process of lab scale epoxy coupons. Rightward movements of both PZT resonance peaks and structural resonance peaks are good representation of the hardening process. Future study can focus on correlating the changes in electrical signatures to the strength or mechanical properties of the epoxy, such as Poisson's ratio and elastic modulus for real-life application. Development of theoretical model is highly desirable. The use of statistical quantification approaches such as Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) can also be attempted.

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